

COMPASS

Counterfactual dataset of tropical cyclone-affected areas

Deliverable 2.6

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Deliverable 2.6 – Counterfactual dataset of tropical cyclone-affected areas

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Executive summary

The overarching goal of the COMPASS project is to develop a harmonised methodological framework for climate and impact attribution of various complex extremes that include compound, consecutive and cascading hazard events. This report is a description of deliverable D2.6, a dataset of high-resolution factual and counterfactual areas affected by tropical cyclones. It contributes to the COMPASS project's objective of providing currently missing datasets to support tropical cyclone attribution studies and to the Work Package 2 objective of generating a counterfactual dataset of tropical cyclone-affected areas.

The dataset contains high resolution simulations of factual and counterfactual maximum (across time of the event) flood depth and derived flooded areas associated with storm surges induced by tropical cyclones. The factual simulations are based on observed relative water levels, i.e. accounting for long-term sea level rise over the historical period. The counterfactual dataset is created by removing the long-term sea level rise from the water level inputs (Treu et al., 2024). In both cases, the information about TC tracks and wind intensities is derived from the International Best Tracks Archive (IBTrACS) covering the period from 1950 to 2024. To put the historical increase in flooded areas into perspective, we additionally provide data assuming 1m of relative sea level rise along all coastlines. All spatial maps are provided at a 30 arcsec (~1 km) spatial resolution and in netCDF format.

This dataset will be used in Work Package 4 for the second set of Use Cases (UCs) focusing on tropical cyclone attribution in the United States. More generally, we foresee this dataset to be of use for the broader scientific community interested in tropical cyclone attribution studies. It is particularly added to the climate-related forcing of the impact model evaluation and impact attribution part of the third phase of the Intersectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP3a). The dataset (currently v1.0) is available in the ISIMIP repository (doi: [10.48364/ISIMIP.693793](https://doi.org/10.48364/ISIMIP.693793)).

Table of Contents

Executive summary	4
1. Dataset of factual and counterfactual areas affected by tropical cyclones	6
1.1. Methodology	6
1.2. File and variable naming.....	7
2. References	8

1. Dataset of factual and counterfactual areas affected by tropical cyclones

This dataset contains high resolution simulations of factual and counterfactual maximum flood depth and flooded areas associated with storm surges induced by tropical cyclones (TCs) where the factual simulations account for long-term historical sea level rise while the counterfactual excluding its effects. The simulations are generated by the open-source numerical software package for water-wave propagation and inundation GeoClaw (Berger et al., 2011; Mandli & Dawson, 2014). Here, we focus on storm surge-induced coastal flooding and neglect pluvial- and fluvial flooding.

The data is available for all IBTrACS tropical cyclones from 1950 to 2024 where GeoClaw indicates surge induced flooding in the factual or counterfactual simulation and provided at 30 arcsec (approximately 1 km) spatial resolution, in netCDF format. As astronomical tides cannot be imposed as dynamic boundary conditions in GeoClaw the simulations are based on a constant offset to the model's water level where for each storm, the offset is calculated via the FES2014 tidal model (Lyard et al., 2021) assuming minimal, mean and maximum tide at the center of the model domain during the year of data encompassing the storm event.

The factual simulations are based on a reconstruction of water levels relative to the local land height, including vertical land motion (Treu et al., 2024). For the counterfactual simulations, the long-term sea level rise has been removed from the coastal water level inputs (Treu et al., 2024). Storm tracks, wind intensities are identical in the factual and counterfactual simulations, and rainfall is not accounted for at all. GeoClaw only describes coastal flooding induced by the TC induced storm surge. To put the historical increase in flooded areas into perspective, we additionally provide data assuming 1m of relative sea level rise (compared to 1900-1905 average sea levels) along all coastlines, again not changing the TC tracks or wind intensities.

1.1. Methodology

Simulations are based on an updated version of the tropical cyclone surge modeling setup described in (Vogt et al., 2024) and already used for the low-resolution (300 arcsec, approximately 10km) factual simulations of TC induced coastal flooding for COMPASS deliverable D1.4 (Mengel, M. (2024)).

Compared to the previous set-up the simulations for D2.6 are (i) based on revised sea level forcings by (Treu et al., 2024), and (ii) apply the more precise geoid model GOCO06s (Kvas et al., 2021) to reference elevation and water depths. We use the global topo-bathymetric dataset described in (Vogt et al., 2024), combining SRTM15+ v2.3 (Tozer et al., 2019) for bathymetry, CoastalDEM v2.1 (Kulp & Strauss, 2021) for low-lying coastal land, and MERIT-DEM (Yamazaki et al., 2019) for remaining land areas.

Information about historical tropical cyclone tracks stems from the International Best Tracks Archive (IBTrACS) dataset (Knapp et al., 2010). A parametric wind and pressure field model (Holland, 1980) is used to drive the open-source geophysical flow solver GeoClaw (Berger et al., 2011; Mandli & Dawson, 2014). GeoClaw solves the depth-averaged shallow water equations in a regional domain that covers both ocean and potentially flooded land area. The dynamic one-step approach overcomes the separation of models between ocean and land, which is still common in surge modelling (Muis et al., 2016; Sampson et al., 2015). GeoClaw enables a seamless simulation of storm surge inundation from wind forcing at a manageable computational cost, even for large sets of storms where each tropical cyclone event is modelled individually. From the 8248 storms recorded in IBTrACS for the period 1950-2024, 3480 cause coastal flooding (see following paragraph for the definition), either in the factual run or in the counterfactual run forced by the de-trended sea level data and are therefore included in the dataset.

Coastal flooding is defined as flooded areas from the TC-induced coastal surge simulations with a flood depth higher than 10 cm. In both datasets, permanent water bodies and areas with elevations > 10m are masked out, and thus do not contribute to the flooded areas. To determine permanent water bodies, we use the Copernicus Global Surface Water Occurrence dataset (Pekel et al., 2016) in version 1.1, which covers the

period 1984-2019, derived from Landsat imagery at 30 m spatial resolution and consider a grid cell to belong to a permanent water body if it was flooded for more than 5 % of the times in the observational period.

1.2. File and variable naming

The factual and counterfactual datasets (doi:[10.48364/ISIMIP.693793](https://doi.org/10.48364/ISIMIP.693793)) are included into the ISIMIP3a climate-related forcing data (primary input data) while the simulations assuming 1m of relative sea level rise do not belong to the ISIMIP3a protocol. Therefore, they are made accessible as secondary input data (doi:[10.48364/ISIMIP.693793](https://doi.org/10.48364/ISIMIP.693793)). The 'obsclim' and 'counterclim' naming conventions follows the attribution framework of the third simulations round of the Intersectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP, (Frieler et al., 2024))

The naming of each file is such that it mentions:

- The coastal model (*geoclaw*)
- Whether is a factual run accounting for the historical sea level rise relative to the 1900-1905 reference period (*obsclim*) or a counterfactual run (*counterclim* or *1mslr*)
- The period of interest, here only historical (*historical*)
- Which flood variable is reported: maximum flood depth (*f1ddph*) or flooded areas (*f1darea*). Flooded areas are stored as a binary variable.
- The coastal water level offset at the center of the model domain during the year of data encompassing the storm event: either minimal (*tidesmin*), mean (*tidesmean*) and maximum tide (*tidesmax*)
- The spatial resolution, here 30 arcsecond
- The sea-level rise scenario, either as observed (*defaultslr*), or assuming no sea level rise (*noslr*) in the counterfactual simulations (with a reference year of 1900-1905)
- The simulated year, from 1950 until 2024

There is one NetCDF file per year, from 1950 until 2024 that stores per storm that caused coastal flooding spatial maps of maximum flood depth and flooded areas. The naming of each storm refers to their IBTrACS name.

Example filenames:

`geoclaw_obsclim_historical_f1darea_tidesmax_30arcsec_1950.nc`

`geoclaw_counterclim_historical_f1darea_tidesmax_30arcsec_1950.nc`

`geoclaw_1mslr_historical_f1darea_tidesmax_30arcsec_1950.nc`

2. References

- Berger, M. J., George, D. L., LeVeque, R. J., & Mandli, K. T. (2011). The GeoClaw software for depth-averaged flows with adaptive refinement. *Advances in Water Resources*, 34(9), 1195–1206.
- Frieler, K., Volkholz, J., Lange, S., Schewe, J., Mengel, M., del Rocío Rivas López, M., Otto, C., Reyer, C. P. O., Karger, D. N., Malle, J. T., Treu, S., Menz, C., Blanchard, J. L., Harrison, C. S., Petrik, C. M., Eddy, T. D., Ortega-Cisneros, K., Novaglio, C., Rousseau, Y., ... Bechtold, M. (2024). Scenario setup and forcing data for impact model evaluation and impact attribution within the third round of the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP3a). *Geoscientific Model Development*, 17(1), 1–51.
- Holland, G. J. (1980). An Analytic Model of the Wind and Pressure Profiles in Hurricanes. *Monthly Weather Review*, 108(8), 1212–1218.
- Knapp, K. R., Kruk, M. C., Levinson, D. H., Diamond, H. J., & Neumann, C. J. (2010). The International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS). *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 91(3), 363–376.
- Kulp, S., & Strauss, B. (2021). CoastalDEM v2.1: A high-accuracy and high-resolution global coastal elevation model trained on ICESat-2 satellite lidar. *Climate Central Scientific Report*. <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=wJ49pwEAAAAJ&hl=en&oi=sra>
- Kvas, A., Brockmann, J. M., Krauss, S., Schubert, T., Gruber, T., Meyer, U., Mayer-Gürr, T., Schuh, W.-D., Jäggi, A., & Pail, R. (2021). GOCO06s – a satellite-only global gravity field model. *Earth System Science Data*, 13(1), 99–118.
- Lyard, F. H., Allain, D. J., Cancet, M., Carrère, L., & Picot, N. (2021). FES2014 global ocean tide atlas: design and performance. *Ocean Science*, 17(3), 615–649.
- Mandli, K. T., & Dawson, C. N. (2014). Adaptive mesh refinement for storm surge. *Ocean Modelling*, 75, 36–50.
- Mengel, M. (2024). Dataset of tropical cyclone-affected areas (D1.4) (v1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14547984>
- Muis, S., Verlaan, M., Winsemius, H. C., Aerts, J. C. J. H., & Ward, P. J. (2016). A global reanalysis of storm surges and extreme sea levels. *Nature Communications*, 7, 11969.
- Pekel, J.-F., Cottam, A., Gorelick, N., & Belward, A. S. (2016). High-resolution mapping of global surface water and its long-term changes. *Nature*, 540(7633), 418–422.
- Sampson, C. C., Smith, A. M., Bates, P. D., Neal, J. C., Alfieri, L., & Freer, J. E. (2015). A high-resolution global flood hazard model: A HIGH-RESOLUTION GLOBAL FLOOD HAZARD MODEL. *Water Resources Research*, 51(9), 7358–7381.
- Tozer, B., Sandwell, D. T., Smith, W. H. F., Olson, C., Beale, J. R., & Wessel, P. (2019). Global bathymetry and topography at 15 arc sec: SRTM15+. *Earth and Space Science (Hoboken, N.J.)*, 6(10), 1847–1864.
- Treu, S., Muis, S., Dangendorf, S., Wahl, T., Oelsmann, J., Heinicke, S., Frieler, K., & Mengel, M. (2024). Reconstruction of hourly coastal water levels and counterfactuals without sea level rise for impact attribution. *Earth System Science Data*, 16(2), 1121–1136.
- Vogt, T., Treu, S., Mengel, M., Frieler, K., & Otto, C. (2024). Modeling surge dynamics improves coastal flood estimates in a global set of tropical cyclones. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 5(1), 1–19.

Deliverable 2.6 – Counterfactual dataset of tropical cyclone-affected areas

Yamazaki, D., Ikeshima, D., Sosa, J., Bates, P. D., Allen, G. H., & Pavelsky, T. M. (2019). MERIT Hydro: A high-resolution global hydrography map based on latest topography dataset. *Water Resources Research*, 55(6), 5053–5073.